

REPORT:

TESTS DEVELOPED ON REDUCE-SCALE REINFORCED ROCKFALL EMBANKMENTS LOADED IN QUASI-STATIC MODE

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1. OBJECTIVE

The experimental campaign aimed to reproduce and analyse the instant of collapse of a reinforced rockfall protection embankment (RE-RPE) in function of two specific reinforcement technologies: Terramesh system from Maccaferri, which includes the use of clips as joint punctual elements among the elements, and a wrap-around system with extruded unidirectional HDPE geogrid.

In particular, to identify the geometric configuration preceding the collapse condition and provide a definition of RE-RPE collapse not currently available in literature.

The experimental campaign took place between 4-6 September 2024.

2. METODOLOGY

Two RE-RPEs were built, one with Terramesh system and the other with wrap-around geogrid system. The embankments were constructed in a reduced scale with a scale factor $\lambda=5$, applying a specific scale law obtained using the Buckingham theorem.

As shown in Figure 6, after the construction, a trust was applied by means of a punch (steel plate) pushed by an instrumented hydraulic jack. This was to reproduce the field of displacements produced by an impacting block at different depths, until the ultimate collapse deformation is reached.

Details are given below.

2.1. SCALLING LAW

The scaling law was derived by means of the Buckingham theorem. The quantities chosen as fundamental are 5 and depend on 3 units of measurement, therefore the 5-3 basic terms to describe the problem have been defined:

$$\pi_1 = \frac{a \cdot \rho \cdot l^3}{F} = [-] \quad \pi_2 = \varepsilon = [-]$$

From a practical point of view, the actual implementation of the scaling law is conditioned by the inability to scale gravity and the challenging in to found a reinforcement suitable with the scaling law

Given the scaling factors of the fundamental quantities λ^i , those of the other quantities were derived:

Fundamental quantities	Scale factor	Derivative quantities	Scale factor
Length l	λ	Mass m	λ^3
Acceleration a	1	Time t	$\lambda^{1/2}$
Density ρ	1	Velocity v	$\lambda^{1/2}$
Force F	λ^3	Pressure p	1
Strain ε	1	Stress σ	1
		Ultimate stress of the reinforcement T_{max}	λ^2

2.2. EMPLOYED MATERIALS

Reinforcement

Different materials readily available on the market were tested to identify one that well fit the scaling law. The force-strain curve was measured for each of these. Figure 1 shows the test set-up specially constructed.

Both reinforcement technologies (Terramesh and wrap-around geogrid) have comparable reinforcement tensile strength, in particular $T_{max} \approx 45 \frac{kN}{m}$ at a final deformation of $\varepsilon \approx 10\%$, therefore only one scaled reinforcement was used.

The 15x15 mm square mesh TNT "Rete avicola" was considered the most suitable to reproduce the desired performances (Figure 1b). Figure 2 shows the 10 tensile test curves carried out on this net in order to obtain statistically representative mechanical parameters. The results are shown in Table 1.

Figure 1: [a] Tensile test on double torsion hexagonal net; [b] Tensile test on poultry net.

Figure 2: Tensile test curves on a 15x15 mm square mesh TNT (Rete avicola).

Table 1: Tensile test results

MATERIAL: Rete Avicola	F_{max} [kN/m]	ϵ_{max} [-]
Test 11	1.207	0.30499
Test 12	1.489	0.164188
Test 13	1.423	0.175554
Test 14	1.470	0.152815
Test 15	1.362	0.136101
Test 16	1.263	0.11801
Test 17	0.973	0.216527
Test 18	1.366	0.111786
Test 19	0.959	0.112985
Test 20	1.158	0.152918
Assumed value	1.52	0.171

Filling soil material

The soil used in the construction was chosen with limited fine content and no organic material.

The material was characterized by particle size curve test and Proctor compaction test. The results are shown in Figure 3.

During the construction phases of the RE-RPEs, which will be described below, a compaction test was carried out on site using the sand cone method in accordance with ASTM D 1556-90, which has shown that 4 runs of vibrating plate per layer yield a compaction level greater than 95% of the Proctor optimum density.

In addition, a plate load test was carried out on a layer in accordance with CNR BU 146/92 standard. The test set-up and pressure diagram on the plate (P) versus the average settlements (δ) are shown in Figure 4, while the numerical values in Table 2. These values yield a deformability module 24.2 MPa.

Figure 3: Characterisation of the soil: [a] granulometric curve; [b] Proctor test.

Table 2: Pressure and settlement values recorded during the plate load test.

	P [MPa]	δ [mm]	$\delta - \delta_{precarico}$ [mm]
precarico	0.0201	0.0489	0.0000
carico 1	0.0515	0.3974	0.3485
carico 2	0.1027	1.0271	0.9782
carico 3	0.1512	1.6316	1.5827
carico 4	0.2037	2.3640	2.3151

Figure 4: Plate load test carried out on the first layer of an embankment.

2.3. RE-RPEs scaled

Net of the considerations described above, the characteristic quantities of the scaled embankments and the relative real quantities are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3: Main scalar quantities in the experimental campaign.

Features	Experimental campaign	
	Real	$\lambda=5$
Side bank slopes	67°	67°

Crest of the RE-RPEs	2 m	0.40 m
Height of the RE-RPEs	0.76 m	0.15 m
Number of layer	8	8
Ultimate tensile strength of the reinforcement	$\approx 40 \frac{kN}{m}$	$1.52 \frac{kN}{m}$

Figure 5: Cross section of the RE-RPEs with scale factor $\lambda=5$

3. COSTRUZIONE OF THE RE-RPEs AND TESTS

3.1. Construction phases ($\lambda=5$)

The RE-RPEs were built confined between two walls of concrete blocks (Figure 6). Wooden frames with a geometry equal to the cross section of the RE-RPE were installed on them. Then, the 8 layers of the embankment were assembled using formworks made from wooden boards fixed to the frames. These formworks were removed at the end of the layer construction.

Each layer of the RE-RPE were built with the following procedure (see Figure 6):

- Positioning of the scaled reinforcement (Rete avicola) with a width equal to 70 cm, so that each layer had exactly 6 reinforcing panels to cover the 4 m wide and a slight overlapping.
- Installation of the scaled formworks (Figure 6c).
- Installation of a geotextile only in the side bank zones to prevent the soil leakage.
- Filling of the layer with the selected soil, levelling to reach 15 cm (height of each layer) and compaction with vibrating plate.
- Closure of the layer with the wrapping of the reinforcement equal to 20 cm.

N.B. In the case of RE-RPE with Terramesh, it has added clips spaced 5 cm to reproduce the correct system configuration: this involves joining the adjacent reinforcement panels and the adjacent formworks in 4 directions. Obviously, also the clips properties were been appropriately scaled.

Figure 6: Construction phases of the scaled RE-RPEs. Figure a-b-c-d-e show the construction phases of the layers up to the end of the construction of the two embankments. Figure f shows a detail of the clips for the Terramesh system.

3.2. Tests

The RE-RPEs were stressed by a circular steel plate with a diameter of 30 cm, which was pushed at mid height against the upstream bank to simulate the crater created by an impact block and, consequently, recreate the deformative state that this causes on the whole structure. The thrust operation was carried out by a long stroke hydraulic jack fitted during the test with various extension cables. The jack was fixed to a concrete block (Figure 7). The test continued until the volume affected by the detected collapsed.

The following measurements were taken during the tests:

- The time pressure of the hydraulic jack and, consequently, the force of thrust.
- The Jack displacement.
- The deformation of the down-stream bank of the embankments were measured by continuous photogrammetric network (Figure 8).

Figure 7: Set-up of the trust system.

Figure 8: Photogrammetrical network.

3.3. Considerations about the tests

Figure 9 and Figure 10 show, respectively, the evolution of the resistant mechanism in the case of reinforced with a wrap-around geogrid system and with Terramesh system.

From the images it can be seen that the mechanism does not seem to change significantly either by the volume of soil being extruded downstream or by the clearly visible cracking pattern in the crest. Furthermore, the force-displacement curves obtained from data processing, shown in Figure 11, show how the trends are fully comparable as well as the order of magnitude of the force.

Further numerical back-analysis analyses, to be used as a comparison with the photogrammetric survey, are currently being developed.

Figure 9: Evolution of the resistance mechanism in the case of wrap-around geogrid type reinforcement.

Figure 10: Evolution of the resistance mechanism in the case of Terramesh type reinforcement.

Figure 11: Force-displacement curves recorded on the hydraulic jack.

4. CONCLUSION

The resistant mechanisms obtained with the two reinforcement systems studied seem to be entirely compatible, therefore the main distinctive elements between the two reinforcement systems, that is clips, do not appear to significantly influence the overall behaviour of the embankments.

The proposed test methodology in pseudo-static has proved to be a good way of studying dynamic behaviour under impact conditions. In fact, the same mechanism of sliding downstream of the layers involved observed in the full-scale tests of Peila et al. 2007 was obtained.

The final objective will be to propose a simplified design method under impact conditions that improves those already in use and to provide a definition of structural collapse for this type of works. At present, a numerical model of the systems studied with the software Abaqus/CAE is being calibrated using force-displacement data and the deformities obtained with the continuous photogrammetric network.

These results are also being published in an international journal.